

TECHNOLOGY AND METHODS OF PROPAGATION OF FRUIT SEEDLINGS

¹Khaitov M.A., ²Rasulov I.M., ³Karshiyev J.D.

¹Associate Professor

²Associate Professor

³Assistant

^{1,2,3}Samarkand State University named after Sh. Rashidov, Institute of Agrobiotechnology and Food Safety, Department of Fruit and Vegetable Growing and Viticulture

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13893576>

Abstract. According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, PD-4947, dated February 7, 2017, paragraph 3.3 of the "Action Strategy" regarding five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, as well as the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated March 29, 2018 "On additional measures for the accelerated development of fruit and vegetable growing in the Republic of Uzbekistan", PR-5388, dated October 23, 2019 "On approval of the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030" and PD-3978, dated October 17, 2018 "On additional measures to improve the efficiency of export of fruit and vegetable products to foreign markets", PD-4239 on March 14, 2019 "On measures to develop agricultural cooperation in the field of fruit and vegetable products" the task of modernizing and accelerating the development of "Agriculture" sphere and growing seedlings of fruit crops from high-yielding varieties with new pests are set in terms of sustainable selection and implementation.

Keywords: selection, introduction, vegetative, grafting, cuttings, budding, root bud, nursery, seedlings, tulip, zapgaldok (Elberta), regeneration, shelter (currant), Rosemary, Simirenko, Kandil Sinab, Parmen, seed (apple, pear), pitted apricot, plum, cherry, peach, nut, golden apple (winter golden parmen), Strela apple.

Introduction. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the development of the fruit and vegetable industry, especially horticulture, the transition to market relations by introducing new technologies into the industry, the rapid development of farms require the widespread involvement of qualified specialists in the field of horticulture. One of the most important areas of the rapid development of the horticulture industry is nursery farming. The use of high-quality seedlings when organizing gardens is a guarantee of high income. Of course, in order to achieve such results, it is important for specialists to know the technology of breeding fruit seedlings. Fruit and berry-fruit plants are propagated with seeds and vegetatively. To create new varieties and grow scions, the method of propagation by generative organs is used.

Many fruit and berry plants are pollinated from the outside and form seed; this seed retains the characteristics of two individuals (parents), and the resulting plants are hybrids. Vegetative propagation of fruit and berry-fruit plants is widely used in practice. It is based on the ability to restore (regenerate) the entire organism from a branch, root, leaf, and even a piece of tissue of a certain part of the plant that has the ability to live. These parts of the organs restore the root principle in the mother plant, which gives rise to the root, and from the shoot gives a branch that gives leaves.

Vegetative propagation keeps the plant in a pure state, it is passed on the characteristics of the mother plant. And when it is propagated by the generative method, a hybrid is obtained that has both maternal and paternal traits, and sometimes the most ancient ancestors. There are many methods of vegetative propagation, and the following groups can be distinguished from them: a) cutting branches and roots into parts, dividing bushes, planting cuttings and root cuttings, grafting and other propagation; b) propagation by grafting.

Most cultivated plants are propagated by grafting. In this case, the plant (cultivar) is grafted onto another plant (scion), which grows from a seed in the soil in the form of a cutting or bud (scion). In this case, the cultivated plant grows on the root of another plant (scion). Plants that grow from a branch or part of a root have their own roots.

Apples, pears, quince, apricots, cherries, almonds, peaches are propagated mainly by bud grafting, and grapes, pomegranates, figs, currants - from well-ripened annual branches with overgrown, medium- and small-sized cuttings. In general, small grafts of apple and pear trees grown from quince differ from strongly growing scions by rapid root development and abundant harvest. Grafts of strongly growing seed and seed types of fruits are mainly propagated from seeds, and they are grafted from cultivated varieties of fruits.

The deeper the roots of the grafts are located in the soil layers, the higher the fruit trees connected to them will be, and the harvest will be late, and vice versa, if the roots of the grafts are scaly and located close to the surface of the earth, the branches of the fruit trees grafted onto them will be shorter, and the harvest will be more abundant, but they usually do not last long. For example, apple trees such as Rosemary, Simirenko, Kandil Sinab, Parmen, grafted onto wild forest apple trees or seedlings grown from cultivated apple seeds, are harvested six to seven years after planting in the garden, an average of 100-300 kg in the second year. Each tree at the age of 20 years can produce 500-1000 kg.

When grafted into the garden of the same apple variety, it begins to bear fruit in the third or fourth year and in six or seven years can produce a harvest of up to 50-60 kg. The roots of trees grown on strong grafts are larger and occupy more land, while apple trees associated with gardens and vegetable gardens occupy less land. The stronger the tree branches grow, the stronger the root system develops.

Most often upright trees bear fruit late, and the branches of a spreading tree - early. Cold and drought resistance of trees also depends on grafts. In Uzbekistan, many research works on growing seedlings of fruit crops have been carried out over several years and valuable information has been collected in this area. More detailed information on this issue is presented in a special section devoted to welding.

Since the 1960s, various research works have been carried out on the selection of small grafts for trees of the republic, in various soil and climatic conditions, with seeds (apples, pears), seed apricots, plums, cherries, peaches and based on this, specific recommendations were given for implementation in production. Along with studying the scions in various soil and climatic conditions, their physiological compatibility with grafts and their inclusion in the harvest were carefully studied. As a result of many years of observation, it was found that not every fruit variety is suitable for every graft.

For example, the apple tree Winter Gold (Parmen Zimny Zolotoy), the apple tree varieties White do not grow well in many grafts. On the other hand, when grafted onto many apple tree seedlings, Calendula Sinap and White Rosemary grow quickly, and the tree branches grow well.

Good adhesion of the scion has a great influence on the number of shoots and their quality. In particular, when planting seedlings in the garden that are poorly connected to the graft, swellings, cracks, warping and similar points of discrepancy between the scion and shoot are often clearly visible in the grafted part.

For example, when a cherry is attached to a pavement cherry, it is often possible to see that the cherry has grown from the place of attachment. When grafting a cherry bud onto a 60-100 cm long part of a cherry tree trunk, it is clear that the cherry has grown a lot, and the cherry has become thinner. Some gardeners are of the opinion that it is possible to propagate such fruits as peaches and walnuts. If you approach this issue from a scientific point of view, then the varieties of fruit crops are mainly pollinated by bees, and it has already been established that a new organism created by propagating one, two or three organisms will not fully transmit the parental characteristics in the future. For example, when Lola and Zafaldok (Elberta) peach seeds are planted, peach trees grown in the future will slowly lag behind in growth. Walnuts also have this feature. Growing walnut seedlings by grafting is much easier than other fruits. When propagating peaches from seeds, they become bitter, and the quality of the harvest deteriorates somewhat. Growing fruit trees by grafting a bud takes some time and a lot of effort. In subsequent years, the achievements of scientific organizations in rooting green and ripe fruits in a special greenhouse with 95-98% air humidity with artificial fog were included in the ashes. This time we will stop in a special section.

As it can be seen from the above, growing fruit seedlings is fundamentally different from growing seedlings of other plants and requires a lot of time and experience. When growing fruit seedlings, it is very important to organize gardens adapted to local soil and climatic conditions. Because, especially when young seedlings resistant to soil salinity are grown in local conditions, they are somewhat resistant to winter cold and salinity compared to grafted fruit seedlings and trees. But fruit trees grown from seed are resistant to both cold and soil salinity.

In the conditions of Karakalpakstan, various types of scions brought from different regions were planted for several years, and as a result of their monitoring, the resistance of apple, pear, quince and other fruits to saline soils was noted and valuable information was obtained. On average, the fruiting percentage of pear varieties grafted onto Ussuri pear seedlings was 96%, and 92% of those grafted onto forest pear saplings. Pear varieties hold up very well on these two grafts. Ussuri pear differs in size and fruitfulness from forest pear.

The yield from a 28-year-old pear tree grafted onto a bud graft to an Assyrian pear was 380 kilograms, and from one large tree grafted onto a forest pear plant - 260 kilograms. In the conditions of Karakalpakstan, it is recommended to propagate the pear varieties recommended in the above-mentioned grafts and plant them on large areas in farms of the republic. There are two varieties of Khazorasp apples, both moderately winter-hardy. The difference between them is that the second one does not have small branches. This type of apple, which produces a small branch, is intolerant of soil salinity and does not grow well in areas near groundwater. In addition, one- and two-year-old branches are severely damaged by the cold.

There is also a tendency to bear fruit. When grafted onto branches, the percentage of bruising of grafted buds did not exceed 82% (when analyzed in the fall). In the conditions of Bukhara, shoots attached to the sprouts of the seed of apple tree turn blue much better. Such apple trees grow well until they reach 80 years of age. The height of the trees is 10-12 m, the width of

the branch circle is 7-8 m. In addition, other advantages of this type of apple trees have been identified.

First of all, this type of apple tree is resistant to soil salinity, grows well even with close groundwater, and yields a harvest every year. Up to 400 kg of fruit were collected from some trees. When grafting apple tree seedlings, the retention of graft buds was up to 97%, and it was also found that they attach well to the grafts. For almost all types of fruit trees in the main zones of the republic, resistant grafts adapted to soil conditions have been identified, developed and recommended. At the same time, in recent years, promising transplants have been brought from most regions of our Republic and foreign countries, which are being tested in various conditions.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No. PD-4947 "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan".
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 29, 2018 N. PR-5388 "On additional measures for the accelerated development of fruit and vegetable production in the Republic of Uzbekistan".
3. Mirzaev M.M., Ph.D. Sobirov - Gardening., T., 1987.
4. Mirzaev M.M., MD Sobirov - Gardening in Uzbekistan, T., 1980.
5. Ostonakulov T.E., Kholmiraev B.Kh. - Walnut varieties and cultivation technology. Samarkand, 2017.
6. Ostonakulov T.E., Akhmedzhanov Zh.A., Kholmiraev B.Kh. - Cultivation technology in Chilonji in Uzbekistan. Samarkand, 2016.